

A descriptive study to assess the level of knowledge regarding hazards of nicotine among students of selected colleges of Gandhinagar district, Gujarat

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Abstract:

Tobacco is a leading preventable cause of deaths worldwide; the situation is particularly serious in the developing countries. Tobacco use among the children and adolescents is already a pandemic and they are vulnerable targets of tobacco industry. This is also the case in India. Revised health belief model of rosenstoch is used as a conceptual framework. In this descriptive survey study, samples are college students of selected college of gandhinagar district and 200 samples are collected by using of simple random sampling technique. Structured knowledge questionnaire was designed to test their level of knowledge regarding hazards of nicotine. In this study 17-19 year of students found 34%, 20-22 year found 55.5% & 23-25 year found 10.5%, so the calculated value of the Chi square test for the age is 22.01 and the tabulated value is 9.49, and it's indicate the significance association. In this study 1st year students found 03%, 2nd year found 37.5% & 3rd year found 59.5%, so the calculated value of the Chi square test for the academic year is 22.58 and tabulated value is 9.49, and it's indicate the significance association. The result of the study shows that the 9.5% samples had poor knowledge, 37.5% samples had average knowledge and 53% samples had good knowledge regarding hazards of nicotine. This result revealed that there has significant association between knowledge with age and knowledge with academic year. The findings of the study revealed that the college students have average knowledge regarding hazards of nicotine it was found to be effective, beneficial and feasible to implement in all settings.

Keywords:

Descriptive study¹, Knowledge², Hazards³, Nicotine⁴

1. Introduction:

"Today's adolescents are tomorrow's citizens."

- Jawaharlal Nehru

Tobacco use in children and adolescents is reaching pandemic levels as they are the most vulnerable population to initiate tobacco use. It is well established that most of the adult users of tobacco, start the use of tobacco either in their childhood or adolescence. Parents are the best route to reach a child and can help lead to bring better outcomes for children. The objectives of the study were to assess the knowledge regarding hazards of nicotine & to find out association between knowledge regarding hazards of nicotine with the selected demographic variables among students. Hence, the aim of this study is to assess the knowledge, regarding the hazards of tobacco use and Cigarette and Other Tobacco Products Act (COTPA) among the parents visiting paediatric dental clinic. Tobacco is a leading preventable cause of deaths worldwide; the situation is particularly serious in the developing countries. The purpose of the study is to develop new ways to measure nicotine dependence severity that may be useful in predicting success in smoking cessation and in development of new smoking cessation treatment targets. Nicotine is also a psychoactive and addictive substance that directly acts on brain areas involved in emotional and cognitive processing (National Institute of Health (GOV)).

About 13 million are non-smokers who die because they are exposed to second hand smoke. Typical cigarettes contain between 1 to 2 milligrams of nicotine, which is about 0.2% of the total weight of the cigarettes. Survey also predicted that 8.5% and 11.7% will smoke in 2023 (WHO, 2023). In 2023 about 1 of every 100 high schools students (1.7%) reported using nicotine pouches in the past 30 days. Nicotine pouches are microfibers pouches with flavoured nicotine powders that user dissolve in mouth without spitting. Routes of exposure nicotine can be absorbed into the body by inhalation, ingestion, skin contact and mucous membranes and because of all these problem is related to health prevent it by taking some information with ourselves. And make sure about our family have to also with no intake of hazards tobacco which is having this nicotine substance (Centre of Disease Control and Prevention). More than 1 million adults die each year in India due to tobacco use accounting for 9.5% of overall deaths Cigarette smoking is estimated to cause the following: More than 480,000 deaths annually (including deaths from second hand smoke) More people die from lung cancer than any other type of cancer Cigarette smoking is the number one risk factor for lung cancer, it's responsible for close to 90% of lung cancer cases (National Library of Medicine 2021). About 1.3 million are non-smokers who die because they are exposed to second hand smoke. Typical cigarettes contain between 1 to 2 milligrams of nicotine, which is about 0.2% of the total weight of the cigarettes. Survey also predicted that 8.5% and 11.7% will smoke in 2023 (WHO, 2023). In 2023 about 1 of every 100 high schools students (1.7%) reported using nicotine pouches in the past 30 days. Nicotine pouches are microfibers pouches with flavored nicotine powders that user dissolve in mouth without spitting. Routes of exposure nicotine can be absorbed into the body by inhalation, ingestion, skin contact and mucous membranes and because of all this problems related to health we have to prevent it by taking some information with ourselves. And make sure about our family also. With no intake of hazards tobacco which having this nicotine substance. (Center of Disease Control and Prevention).

The estimates that more than 8 million people die prematurely yearly from tobacco use. Tobacco is a major risk factor for many chronic diseases, including cancer, Lung disease, cardiovascular disease and stroke. It is one of the major causes of death and disease in India and accounts for nearly 1.35 million deaths every year (WHO, 2018). Every Sixteen percent of the study population (29.3% men and 23% women) smoked tobacco, 20% of the study population (28.1% men and 12.0% women) chewed tobacco/panmasala, and 30% of the study population (46.5% men and 13.8% women) either smoked or chewed tobacco. The overall lifetime prevalence of tobacco use was 6.9% (12.5% males and 12% females). The prevalence of tobacco use increased from 3.1% at 12-13 year to 15.1% at 18-19 year. About 20 million children of ages 10-14 are estimated to be tobacco-addicted according to a survey done by the National Sample Survey Organization of the Indian Government. To this as to undoing figure, about 5500 new users are added daily, making two million new users every year. (Health and Social Services, 2016).

2. Methods & material:

200 samples were taken for the study with the use of Non probability simple random sampling study. The Karl Pearson formula was used to find out the reliability of data. This statement was used to research with the current need of knowledge in the students regarding the hazards of nicotine.

2.1. Research design:

The present study is a descriptive study to assess the level of knowledge regarding hazards of nicotine among student of selected college in Gandhinagar district, Gujarat. The descriptive survey research approach is considered the most appropriate with their selected demographic variables. (I.e. Age, Gender, History of consumption, socioeconomic status, current users). In this study the Simple random sampling technique was used to select the samples. Research variables are Level of knowledge regarding hazards of nicotine among college students. Structure knowledge questionnaire was formed to assess the level of knowledge regarding hazards of nicotine among college students of selected colleges. The conceptual framework for this study is based on the revised Health Belief Model which was one of the firsts and remains one of the best known social cognition models. Health belief is person's attitude and idea about health and illness. There may be factual information or wrong information. The assumption in this model is that college student may have some knowledge regarding hazards of nicotine. So the investigator felt Rosenstoch [2003] revised Health Belief Model is suitable as conceptual framework for A descriptive study to assess the level of knowledge regarding hazards of nicotine among students of selected college in Gandhinagar district, Gujarat.

2.2. Research settings:

The college were selected on the basis of feasibility of conducting study and availability of sample. A pilot study was conducted at Samarpan arts & Commerce College, Gandhinagar. In the pilot study 20

samples were taken from the setting. The samples were selected through simple random sampling method. A main study was conducted at Ashwinbhai A. Patel Commerce College, Gandhinagar on the 200 college student.

Research criteria for sample:

2.3. Inclusion criteria:

1. Samples that are belong from commerce field & willingly to participate.
2. Samples present at the time of data collection to participate in this study.

2.4. Exclusion criteria:

1. Those who are not belong from commerce stream & willing to participate.
2. Not available at the time of data collection.
3. Students belonging from below 17 year of age.

2.5. Development of tool:

The tool used for study was distributed as follows:

SECTION1: Includes the demographic information of participants such as age, gender, history of consumption, socio economic status, current consummators about assess the level of knowledge regarding hazards of nicotine among the students of selected colleges of Gandhinagar district, Gujarat.

It includes students of colleges studying in selected colleges of Gandhinagar district, Gujarat.

SECTION 2: It consists structured questions related to knowledge on hazards of nicotine. In which included questions regarding which are the ways of nicotine consumption, how it affect the human body, which are the effects on the pregnant woman and baby, what is the social effect among the nicotine users and lesignation about nicotine.

This tool includes all the major criteria for the study. The researcher reviewed related literature to describe the tool to assess the level of knowledge. By using Karl Pearson formula (split half method} Reliability of knowledge questionnaire $r = 0.7821$.

3. Results:

There is a significant association of the knowledge score with age and year of the study and no significant association with gender, family history of nicotine consumption, type of family and current consumption of nicotine. Related to findings knowledge regarding hazards of nicotine this study revealed that majority of students has good level of knowledge is 53%, average level of knowledge is 37.5%, and poor level of knowledge is 9.5%.

4. Discussion:

The data revealed that students of college are having poor level of knowledge regarding hazards of nicotine as well as the male adolescents having more consumption in student life with reference study of Ganavadiya, Rahul; Chandrasekhar etl., and it was found to be effective, beneficial and feasible to implement in their routine & life to prevent more hazards in adolescents. Miss Nighat Parveen & Zahid (May 2023) conducted a research study to evaluate the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding ill effects of cigarette smoking on health among teenage students of a selected higher secondary school of Anantnag, J&K. Majority 21 (70%) of teenage students had average knowledge, 6 (20%) had poor knowledge and 3 (10%) students scored good marks in pre-test but in the post-test, majority 24 (80%) had good knowledge and 6 (20%) of them scored average level of knowledge and none of them 0 (0%) was having poor level of knowledge. The result showed that there was a significant difference between pre-test and post-test level of knowledge regarding ill effects of cigarette smoking on health among teenage students.

Table. 1: Analysis and interpretation for association between knowledge and demographic variables regarding hazards of nicotine

<i>Sr.no.</i>	<i>Demographic variables</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
1	Age a)17- 19 Years b) 20-22 Years c) 23-25 Years	68 111 21	34% 55.5% 10.5%
2	Gender a)Male b)Female c) Transgender	80 120 00	40% 60% 00%
3	Family history of nicotine consumption a)Yes b) No	56 144	28% 72%
4	Type of family a)Joint b) Nuclear	110 90	55% 45%
5	Current consumption of nicotine a) Yes b) No	37 163	18.5% 81.5%
6	Academic year a) 1 st year	06	03%

b) 2 nd year	75	37.5%
c) 3 rd year	119	59.5%

Table. 2: significant Association between age and knowledge

Age	Knowledge			Total	Calculated value of χ^2	Tabulated value of χ^2
	Good	Average	Poor			
17-19 year	33	35	0	68	22.01	9.49
20-22 year	61	31	19	111		
23-25 year	12	9	0	21		
Total	106	75	19	200		

Significance at 0.05 level, DF (4) $\chi^2= 9.49$

Table. 3: significant Association between academic year and knowledge

Academic year	Knowledge			Total	Calculated value of χ^2	Tabulated value of χ^2
	Good	Average	Poor			
1 st year	06	0	0	06	22.58	9.49
2 nd year	34	40	1	75		
3 rd year	66	35	18	119		
Total	106	75	19	200		

Significance at 0.05 level, DF (4) $\chi^2= 9.49$

Table. 4: scoring based on knowledge of students

S.no.	Category	Knowledge (%)
1	Good knowledge	53%
2	Adequate knowledge	37.5%
3	Poor knowledge	9.5%

Figure. 1: analysis and interpretation of the demographic variables of the samples

Figure. 2: scoring based on knowledge of students

5. Reference:

- (1) Basvanthappa, B. T. (2003). *Nursing research.*(Pp- 957-964).
- (2) Best, J. W., & Kahn, J. V. (2013). *Research in education: Pearson new international edition* (10th Ed.). Pearson Education.
- (3) Jacob, A. (n.d.). *A Comprehensive textbook of midwifery & gynecological nursing.* (Pp- 90-93)
- (4) Mp Sharma, M. (n.d.). *Adult health nursing-1.*
- (5) Subash Indra, C. L. (n.d.). *A text book of psychiatry and mental health nursing.* EMMES Publishers. (Pp- 428-429)
- (6) Journals: Banks, E., Joshy, G., Weber, M. F., Liu, B., Grenfell, R., Egger, S., Paige, E., Lopez,

- A. D., Sitas, F., & Beral, V. (2015). Tobacco smoking and all-cause mortality in a large Australian cohort study: findings from a mature epidemic with current low smoking prevalence. *BMC Medicine*, 13(1), 38. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-015-0281-z>
- (7) Chadda, R. K., & Sengupta, S. N. (2003). Tobacco use by Indian adolescents. *Tobacco Induced Diseases*, 1(2), 111.
- (8) Chadda, R. K., & Sengupta, S. N. (2003b). Tobacco use by Indian adolescents. *Tobacco Induced Diseases*, 1(1), 8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1617-9625-1-8>
- (9) Dhafer, S. A., Rethaiaa, A., Saleh Al Mutairi, A., Saleh Al Rashidi, T., & Hamoud Al Rasheedi, H. (n.d.). *Saad Amer Journal of International Society of Preventive and Community Dentistry*. Al Rasheedi.
- (10) Heasman, L., Stacey, F., Preshow, P. M., McCracken, G. I., Hepburn, S., & Heisman, P. A. (2006). The effect of smoking on periodontal treatment response: a review of clinical evidence. *Journal of Clinical Periodontology*, 33(4), 241–253. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-051x.2006.00902.x>
- (11) Janik-Konieczny, K., Zatoński, T., Połtyn-Zaradna, K., Zatońska, K., Cedzyńska, M., Przeźniak, K., & Wojtyła, A. (2012). An attempt to assess knowledge about tobacco dependence among students at the Medical University in Wrocław. *Annals of Agricultural and Environmental Medicine: AAEM*, 19(3), 345–349.
- (12) Jha, P., & Chaloupka, F. J. (1999). *Curbing the Epidemic: Governments and the Economics of Tobacco Control*.
- (13) Murad, J. E. (n.d.). *Habit of Smoking and Consumption of Alcohol in Brazil*. Tobacco Counters.
- (14) Pal, R., Tsering, D., & Dasgupta, A. (2010). Substance use among adolescent high school students in India: A survey of knowledge, attitude, and opinion. *Journal of Pharmacy & Bioallied Sciences*, 2(2), 137.
- (15) Park-Lee, E., Jamal, A., Cowan, H., Sawdey, M. D., Cooper, M. R., Birdseye, J., West, A., & Cullen, K. A. (2024). *Notes from the field: E-cigarette and nicotine pouch use among middle and high school students — United States, 2024*. *MMWR. Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, 73(35), 774–778. <https://doi.org/10.15585/mmwr.mm7335a3>.
- (16) Rahul, Pallavi, Ruchika, Rana, P., & Tomar. (2018). double by 2020 if death due to tobacco continues to occur at the same rate. *Shubham Less Industrial Psychiatry Journal*, 27(1), 27–40.
- (17) Rai, B., & Bramhankar, M. (2021). Tobacco use among Indian states: Key findings from the latest demographic health survey 2019–2020. *Tobacco Prevention & Cessation*, 7(March), 1–2. <https://doi.org/10.18332/tpc/132466>
- (18) *Seattle: Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation*. (n.d.).

- (19) Siddiqi, K., Husain, S., & Vidyasagaran, A. (2020). Global burden of disease due to smokeless tobacco consumption in adults: an updated analysis of data from 127 countries. *BMC Med*, 18.
- (20) Singh, D. M., Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Government Medical College, Amritsar (Punjab), India, Bala, D. N., Garg, D. P. D., Bansal, D. S., Bumrah, D. S., Attri, D. A., Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Government Medical College, Amritsar (Punjab), India, Professor and Head, Department of Psychiatry, Government Medical College, Amritsar (Punjab), India, Junior Resident, Department of Psychiatry, Government Medical College, Amritsar (Punjab), India, Undergraduate Student, SGRD Medical College, Amritsar (Punjab), India, & Undergraduate Student, Thapar University, Patiala (Punjab), India. (2017). Substance abuse in Children and adolescent: A Retrospective Study. *International Journal of Medical Research and Review*, 5(3), 352–356. <https://doi.org/10.17511/ijmrr.2017.i03.22>
- (21) Souza, d', & Markou, M. S. (2011). Neuronal mechanisms underlying development of nicotine dependence: implications for novel smoking-cessation treatments. *Addiction Science & Clinical Practice*, 6(1), 4–16.
- (22) Tiwari, R. V., Megalamanegowdru, J., Gupta, A., Agrawal, A., Parakh, A., Pagaria, S., & Sahu, A. (2015). Knowledge, attitude and practice of tobacco use and its impact on oral health status of 12 and 15 year-old school children of Chhattisgarh, India. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention: APJCP*, 15(23), 10129–10135. <https://doi.org/10.7314/apjcp.2014.15.23.10129>.
- (23) Vadhel, U., Reddy, A., & Doss, J. J. (2021). A Study to Evaluate the Effectiveness of Structured teaching program on smoking hazards in terms of Knowledge among Adolescent boys in selected Colleges at Rajkot. *Asian J. Nursing Education and Research*, 11(1), 145–147.
- (24) Vyas, M. J., & Patel, A. B. (2016). A KAP study on tobacco use among school children of Ahmedabad. *Int J Res Med*, 5(02), 84–87.
- (25) Warren, C. W., Riley, L., Asma, S., Eriksen, M. P., Green, L., Blanton, C., Loo, C., Batchelor, S., & Yach, D. (2000). Tobacco use by youth: a surveillance report from the Global Youth Tobacco Survey project. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 78(7), 868–876. (N.d). Who.int. Retrieved July 5, 2025.
- (26) (N.d-b). Ajner.com. Retrieved July 5, 2025, from <https://ajner.com/AbstractView.aspx?PID=2021-11-1-37>.